

HOW TO CHOOSE SUITABLE ACTIVITY FOR EFL CLASSROOMS?

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Abstract: *In this article, I provided useful information how to choose suitable activities for EFL classrooms. As so, you are given detailed information about how to use and whom to use this activity.*

Keywords: *target learners, auditory learners, “hanging man” game, problem-solving skills, perfectionist, the Victorian era.*

My target learners consist of 12 students who study at school at 7th grade. Their ages are between 13-14 year old and there are 5 girls and 7 boys. Their goal is to get CEFR or multi-level certificate in order to enter the University. All of them have great interest in learning English language. Some of them attend language courses additionally. Recently, I have taken mock exam and according to the results 8 of them are pre-intermediate and 4 of them are elementary. They are representatives of Uzbek and Kazakh nationalities. Their first languages are Uzbek and Kazakh. Additionally, they know Russian as well. I conduct my lessons in special English classroom that was designed and equipped appropriately. They use their mother tongue at home and with their friends, but I try to keep English atmosphere in my lessons as much as possible. My target learners are mostly auditory learners and I use video and listening materials a lot according to their needs. In fact our lesson lasts 45 minutes, however I try to manage the time and to complete all tasks. They want to increase all 4 language skills such as speaking, listening, reading, writing and listening. They are good at speaking when it comes to ordinary topics. As so they can write texts about daily topics as well. They should boost their vocabulary in order to be perfectionist in speaking and writing skill. So, when I planning my lessons I often add vocabulary activities. Their favorite task is translating English texts in their own language or vice versa. When it comes reading skill, they like to read simple, low level texts. After reading, they usually discuss them in groups. However, all of them good at receptive skills and my task is to improve their productive skills. As XXI century is technology era, we cannot imagine our lessons without technological

tools such as TV, notebook, electronic board and mobile phones. Even we can use pupils' mobile phones appropriately. All of them have opportunity to access network as they have Wi-fi connection at home and at school. As I mentioned every lesson I do vocabulary task, for this I use interactive and interesting game named “hanging man”. This game is very engaging and motivating that makes to participate even passive students. They use their mobile devices only for educational purposes; otherwise they switch of during the lesson.

Description of my activity.

Choosing appropriate activity is very problematic issue, as we should take into account their age, cultural background, religious belief and interest. Most students have difficulty learning new words because of laziness or bad memory. Every lesson I give them new words with their definition and ask them to learn them by heart. Then I mention that we will play game “hanging man” in order to check their vocabulary knowledge. During the game I gather their all books and notebooks in order not to give chance for cheating.

“Hanging man” is old activity; however it is still in use. In this game, learners' task will be to find missing words. In this game group will be divided into two groups, their task is to tell missing letter turn by turn. If they say correct letter, that letter will be appeared on electronic board. Then they should try to guess the whole word, if they say wrong letter they lose a life and hangman appears peace by peace. Their goal is to find the correct answer and save that man. kind of activity helps my learners to revise their vocabulary and at the same time sharp their spelling and word-decoding skills. My learners can particularly improve their concentration.

Also my learners develop their problem-solving skills by trying to guess and figure out letters to fill in. It is safe game and avoids monotony as other games have. It develops tolerance in my learners, as they are adolescence they are very emotional in this age. However, this kind of game makes them to save the life by simply solving the problem. And they will have opinions about that every problem has a solution. This game is psychologically appropriate that makes them to think critically. Even it has negative name such as “hanging man”, however it focused on educational purposes. If it was unsafe, it would

not have reached till this time from the Victorian era. Another advantages of this game, you can play even you do not have opportunity to use digital tools because of electricity off or not having such electronic tools at school. You just simply use chalk and blackboard and begin to play by drawing it on the board.

Here I provide a link for my activity; you can be accessed by clicking on this link.

<https://www.hangmanwords.com/play/custom?g=bW90aXZhdGUIMEFyZXNwb25zaWJsZSUwQXJlc3BIY3QIMEFpbXBYb3ZIJTBBC2VsZi1zdHVkeSUwQWh1bWJsZQ==>

Below I provided list of questions related to this game:

1. Gaining knowledge without assistance of teacher or tutor (self-study)
2. Synonym of the word “answerable” (responsible)

3. Feeling deep admiration for someone (respect)
4. Provide with a reason for doing something (motivate)

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